
Alternative Batik Silk on Finishing Process for 100% Viscosa Fabric With Pad-Dry-Cure Method Using Variation Concentration (Stiffener 50) and Curring Temperature

Maya Komalasari¹, NM.Susyami Hitariat^{1*} and Afifah Nurhasanah¹

¹ Politeknik STTT Bandung

* Correspondence: maya.komalasari@yahoo.com, susyami@yahoo.com Tel.: +62-815-7372-3273

Abstract

Batik is one of the riches of Indonesian heritage and characteristics. The basic batik cloth commonly used is derived from cellulose (cotton) and from protein (silk). At present the price of silk continues to increase along with the scarcity of raw materials. As an alternative to silk fabric, 100% viscose fabric is chosen which has the same luster as silk and a good drape ability so that it is referred to as superior drapery. Research on the nature of viscose fabrics to resemble silk needs to be done holistically to improve the crease recovery-resistant properties by controlling the decrease in tensile strength, slenderness so that it is done by refining 80 g / l *dimethylol-dihydroxy-ethylene* urea finish resin and adding additives. The experiment was carried out by varying the concentration of Stiffener 50 5 g / l, 10 g / l, and 15 g / l and curring temperature of 150°C, 160°C and 170°C. Evaluation for the fabric are handling test, ability to return from crease recovery fabric, tensile strength, drape ability and appearance resistance after washing. The test results showed the influence of the concentration of the filler (Stiffener 50) and curring temperature. The higher the concentration of filler and curring temperature, the higher the ability of the fabric to return from crease recovery, tensile strength and drape value, for the value of the handling to visually decrease will be. The result of this study showed that 100% viscose cloth can be used as an alternative to batik silk. The optimum condition based on the handling is obtained by increasing the concentration of filler as much as 10 g / l curring temperature 160°C with ranking 2 (soft), the angle value returns the warp direction and weft 131 °, the value of tensile strength is 7.6 kg and weft to 7.26 kg and drape ability of 0.29708.

Keywords: viscose, pad-dry-cure, finishing, curring

DOI :

1. Introduction

Batik is a handicraft as a result of coloring using wax. It uses hot wax as color resistor and canting, a pen-like tool, as writing utensil for the motifs. The process of making batik cannot be done on all types of fabrics, only fabrics made from natural materials can be used to get maximum result. Fabrics

used for batik must have undamaged properties due to the influence of the batik process and can be colored at cold temperatures or room temperatures because batik wax as a color resistor can not

stand the heat temperature above 70°C. In general, fabrics that have these properties are fabrics made from natural fibers such as cellulose fibers and protein fibers, such as cotton or silk fabrics. Viscose rayon is a fabric made from fibers produced by cellulose regeneration. Viscose rayon structure is the same as other cellulose fibers, with the advantage of physical properties that look luster, and good absorption like silk. However, this 100% viscose fabric has smaller slack value compared to silk, and is with high crease recovery when compared to silk[1,2]. Seen from its resilience, silk cloth has a fairly good resilience compared to the low viscose fabric resilience, so that silk wrinkle resistance is better than viscose fabric. To find alternative raw materials for batik silk, 100% viscose cloth needs to be improved by using an anti-wrinkle resin (Knittex FEL). Wrinkle resin (Knittex FEL) has a chemical composition in the form of dimethyloldihydroxy-ethylene urea (DMDHEU) which is a reactant resin which tends to form short polymers but many are cross-linked with molecular cellulose (viscose). In refining finish resin this requires a catalyst to accelerate the rate of chemical reactions without experiencing changes in chemical reactions. The amount of catalyst used depends on the amount of anti-wrinkle resin which is 30% from the use of anti-wrinkle resin. The use of catalysts requires a high acidic pH of 3.5-4.5, but, in 100% viscose fibers, the acids will break the chains of glucose molecules in the cellulose chain so that hydrocellulose will be formed. The hydrocellulose causes a decrease in tensile strength in 100% viscose fibers. To prevent a decrease in tensile strength, a filler containing polyvinyl acetate (Stiffener 50) is needed. Therefore, it is necessary to find the optimum concentration of filler by varying the filler (Stiffener 50) by 5 g / l, 10 g / l and 15 g / l so that it has good resilience without reducing the strength of the viscose fabric. The addition of Stiffener 50, besides preventing a decrease in tensile strength, also gives a stiffer grip effect on 100% viscose fabric so that it can make the viscose fabric straightness resemble the straightness of silk fabrics. The handle that becomes rigid certainly makes the viscose cloth uncomfortable to wear. On the other hand, the silk cloth has a soft grip, so a softener has to be added to make the handle on the 100% viscose fabric resemble silk. Softener substances used are nonionic or slightly cationic in order to obtain permanent soft properties because in general the fibers in the negatively charged water and cationic softening agents are positively charged. This will make the softening agent react and makes a permanent soft property of the fabric and decreases the conductivity of the electricity.

Based on the results, it is necessary to analyze the resin finish refinement process by varying the concentration of filler (Stiffener 50) and curring temperature variations on the fabric resilience to determine whether the filler used can improve the resilience of 100% viscose fabric without reducing its tensile strength. To obtain optimum conditions from the process of refining viscose fabric finish resins that resemble silk fabric, it is necessary to test the handling, tensile strength, drape ability and repeated washing to obtain the durability of the resin on the fabric.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Viskosa 100% (Dobby, Weight fabric 101,35 g/m² , Silk Fabric 76,78 g/m², Crease recovery resin DMDHEU (Knittex FEL) 85 g/l, Catalis (Knittex *catalyst* Mo) 30 % from Knittex FEL Resin, Filler Polivinil Asetat (Stiffener 50) 5,10,15 g/l, softener polidimetil polisiloksan (Ultratex STS-D) 30 g/l, softener polidimetil polisiloksan (FMI) 20 g/l, polisilikat acid (Formax W) 10g/l.

2.2. Method

Padd-dry-Cure method with WPU 80%, The fabric is squeezed with padding machine then dried with Stenter machine laboratory 100°C for 1-2 menit , and IR Curing with temperature 150°C, 160°C dan 170°C for 2 minutes. Evaluation for the fabric as visual handling, crease recovery ability test (SNI ISO 2313:2011), Tensile strength test (SNI 0276:2009), drape ability (SNI 08-1511-2004), appearance after washing (SNI ISO 0298:2009).

3. Results

3.1. Handling Visual method

Visual assessment of fabric handling can be seen in Table 1. An assessment was carried out to find out the fabric handling that resembles a silk cloth (comparative fabric) which included cloth that was very soft, soft, soft enough, soft and not soft. Assessment is carried out by 5 observers who have experience in the textile field. Assessment can be seen in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1. Handling visual test with Observer assessment

Variation Concentration (PVAc)	Curring temperature	Observer assessment					Total value	value rank
		1	2	3	4	5		
5 g/l	150°C	5	5	5	5	5	25	1
	160°C	5	4	5	5	5	24	1
	170°C	5	4	5	5	4	23	1
10 g/l	150°C	5	4	4	3	4	20	2
	160°C	4	3	3	4	3	17	2
	170°C	2	3	2	3	3	13	3
15 g/l	150°C	2	2	2	3	2	11	3
	160°C	2	1	2	2	1	8	4
	170°C	1	1	1	1	1	5	5

Information for Value Rank for handling test : 1: No soft, 2 less soft ; 3 plenty soft ; 4 : soft ; 5 : very soft

3.2. Crease recovery Angle (SNI ISO 2313:2011)

The average yield of the retest value of fabric crease recovery in the direction of warp and weft after the resin finish refinement process.

Table 2. Crease Recovery angle of warf and weft before and after washing

Average ability crease recovery test (°)												
Variation Concentration (PVAc))	Curring temperature											
	Before washing						After washing					
	150 °C		160 °C		170 °C		150 °C		160 °C		170 °C	
	Warp	Welf	Warp	Welf	Warp	Welf	Warp	Welf	Warp	Welf	Warp	Welf
5 g/l	114	111	125	120	126	124	112	108	119	115	124	119
10 g/l	128	126	131	131	134	133	125	120	127	127	128	129
15 g/l	140	139	143	141	147	146	135	133	139	137	142	141
Viskosa fabric	90						76					
Silk fabric	124,6						117,66					

3.3. Tensile strength

The average of tensile strength in the direction of warp and weft after the resin finish before and after washing.

Table 3. Tensile Strength of warf and weft before and after washing

Variation Concentration (PVAc))	Average of tensile strength (Kg)											
	Curring temperature (°C)											
	Before washing						After washing					
	Warp			Welf			Warp			welf		
	150	160	170	150	160	170	150	160	170	150	160	170
5	6	6,5	7	6	6,2	6,6	4	4,5	4,53	4	4,5	4,8
10	7,2	7,6	7,8	7	7,26	7,67	4,6	4,8	5	5	5,46	6
15	7,83	8	8,68	7,8	8	8,3	7	7,53	8	6,5	7,5	8
Viskosa fabric	7,66			6,66			5			4,5		
Silk	8			7			6,5			6		

3.4. Drape ability

Table 4. Drape ability fabric with variation concentration and curring temperature

Variation Concentration (PVAc)	Curring temperature (°C)		
	150 (°C)	160 (°C)	170 (°C)
5	0,24718	0,25004	0,27176
10	0,27462	0,29708	0,30468
15	0,31098	0,32456	0,3378
Viskosa fabric		0,30923	
Silk		0,50224	

4. Discussion

4.1 Visual Handling method

The average calculation in Table 1, using the ranking method observer standard analysis, shows that at a concentration of 10 g / l filler, with the curring temperature of 160 ° C, viscose fabric 100% handling for silk, looks like same for handling silk fabric. In accordance with the results obtained in the recipe with concentrations of anti-creasing resins, softener additives and the addition of a (Stiffener 50) 5 g / l give a very gentle effect compared to concentrations of 10 g / l and 15 g / l, because of the higher concentration of fillers polyvinyl acetate (Stiffener 50). It also gives the effect of rigid properties and the higher the curring temperature of the heat gives a thick effect on the fabric (bulky). There are 2 softening agents used in this study, namely non-ionic polydimethylsiloxane type softener and cationic type amino-functional polysiloxane which is capable of providing permanent soft properties. This happened because generally the fibers in the negatively charged water and cationic softening agents are positively charged, so that the substance the softener reacts and creates a permanent softness to the fabric. Both of these substances are silk-type softening agents which have excellent softening, excellent soft, very good for slippery. Silicone softeners are also stable in hot temperatures and resistant to repeated washing and good product sharing by forming a film layer on the surface of the fabric and crosslinked. The addition of a polysilicate acid additive (Fornax W) also gives a soft effect to the fabric and makes it easier for the fabric to be sewn and provides an anti-tear effect on the fabric.

4.2 Crease Recovery Angle

The results of testing the fabric back from the viscose fabric tangling can be seen from a graph of the ability to return from warp and weft tangles. Related to the graph above, the back angle of the warp and feed folds, and it was found that the 100% viscose fabric's, after the resin finishing process, value at the back angle of the folds is increased compared to the viscose fabric before the finishing process

of resin finishes. In addition, the return angle of the 100% viscose fabric fold that has been processed has exceeded the return angle value of the silk fabric fold. This shows that the viscose fabric 100 % that has been processed resembled the nature of silk fabric. The increase in the return angle value of the folds is due to the addition of the anti-tangle resin (Knittex FEL New). Dimethyloldihydroxy ethylene urea (DMDHEU) is a type of cyclic reactant resin. This resin is reactive thermosetting, so it can react with itself but react more with cellulose forming crosslinking compound. The resin compound has two active groups which, when heated, can react with the hydroxyl group of cellulose and form a cross bond. The active groups of pracondensate will also bind the -OH group from the adjacent cellulose molecular chain so that a cross bond between the cellulose molecules occurs through methylene bridges or ethylene ether bridges [7], resulting in good tangle-resistant properties. Table 2 shows that the more concentration used, the higher the value of the fabric return angle from the folds is. Polyvinyl, as filler etat, affects the value of the degree of angle back to the fabric. It happens because the filler enters the crevices of the fiber and the fibers become more bonded which are prevented due to mechanical pressure given so that the fibers' shape do not change and becomes resistant to tangles. This can occur because the higher the polymerization temperature concentration results in the resin entering the fiber and polymerizing so that it forms a cross bond between the resin and the cellulose OH group. The ability of the fabric to return from this fold is directly proportional to the greater the concentration of the filler (Stiffener 50) and the curring temperature of the filler. After washing, the ability of the cloth back from the creasing of the warp direction and feed after repeated washing has decreased. The decrease is due to the presence of resins which are lost during repeated washing processes. This can occur because soap has a hydrophobic and hydrophilic group to release resins that are on the surface of the fabric. However, it does not show a decrease of more than 10%, so the resistance to repeated washing is still acceptable.

4.3 Tensile Strength

Basically the tensile strength of viscose fabrics is lower than the silk fabrics. Showed in Table 3, there was a decrease in tensile strength in viscose fabrics which had been processed to refine the finish resin which could be caused by the addition of an anti-tangle resin that requires an acidic atmosphere. The acid in high temperature will break the chains of glucose molecules in the cellulose chain so that hydrocellulose is formed. The hydrocellulose causes a decrease in tensile strength in 100% viscose fibers. The addition of a polyvinyl acetate (Stiffener 50) filler that functions as a substance that fills the fiber cracks is done to increase the weight of the fabric and give a stiff effect so that the fibers get tighter and the tensile strength gets better. This study also uses polysilicate acid (Fornax W) tearing agent which has a polysilicate acid content of 10 g / l to prevent a drastic decrease in tensile strength of the fabric due to the padding process of the fabric experiencing friction due to pressure. Fabrics are worked with substances that have the ability to coat or fill the gaps between threads. Fiber or yarn has a rough surface because of the polymer coating on its surface so that the yarn does not easily shift. The Fornax-w anti-tear substance used has the ability to coat or fill the gaps between threads, and also can give a soft effect on the fabric. Likewise, the higher curring temperature gives an opportunity for acids to hydrolyze the fibers so that more and more chains of molecules break up and cause the tensile strength to decrease. However, in the presence of fillers and the higher use of curring temperature, the chance for fillers to enter the fibers and repair value of fabric tensile strength gets higher.

4.4 Drape ability

Based on the graph, it can be seen that higher concentration of the polyvinyl acetate (Stiffener 50) filler and the curring temperature of the cake gives higher value of the slenderness coefficient of the fabric (more rigid) as showed in figure 1 :

Figure 1. Graph of Drape ability with variation in concentration of Filler PVAc (g/l) and curring temperature

The stiffness is obtained because the filler closes the surface of the fabric by coating. When the layer joins the fiber and binds to produce a stiff effect and is given a hot temperature, it produces a rigid polymer which does not change in repeated washing. However, the concentration of fillers as much as 5 g / l and 10 g / l has not been able to increase the direct coefficient value of the viscose blank. This is due to the use of softener substances (Ultratex STS-D and Ultratex FMI) which are quite a lot that affect the good grip properties of the fabric. When the filler is 15 g / l, the direct coefficient value starts to stabilize (equal to the direct value of the viscose blank) even at curring temperatures of 160°C and 170°C, the direct coefficient value is higher (stiffer) even though the silk coefficient has not been close.

5. Conclusion

The test results of the physical properties of 100% viscose fabric that has been completed by resin finish include crease recovery angle test, the tensile strength of the fabric and drape ability for the fabric. The results of the conclusion are as follows:

1. Based on the calculation of the average value, it is found that the higher the addition of the concentration of the filler (Stiffener 50) and the higher the curring temperature of the filler, the higher the return properties of the folds, the tensile strength of the fabric and the slackness of the fabric are.
2. The optimum condition is based on the fabric handle visually at the concentration of filler (Stiffener 50) as much as 10 g / l curring temperature of 160°C with rank of 2 (soft).

3. The optimum condition based on the results of testing and calculation of the average value of 100% viscose physical properties test that the silk-like value is obtained at the concentration of the filler (Stiffener 50) as much as 10 g / l curring temperature of 160 ° C with the angle value returning to the direction 131 ° and the direction of feed 131 °, the tensile strength of the warp direction is 7.6 kg and the feed direction is 7.26 kg and the slope value is 0.29708.

References

- [1] Billie J. Collier, dkk (2009), *Understanding Textiles Seventh Edition, Volume 10*.
- [2] Hitariat, N.M Susyami, *Technology Textile and Garment Finishing*, Polytechnic STTT Bandung, 2016.
- [3] N,M Susyami Hitariyat, (*Textile Finishing*), School of Textile Technology, 2005.
- [4] Shore,John,. *Colorant and auxiliaries, VOL ii*, Society of Dyers and Colourists, 2002.
- [5] Soeparman, (1977), *Finishing Technology*, Institut Teknologi Tekstil.
- [6] Soeprijono P, dkk, (1973), *Textile Fiber*, Institut Teknologi Tekstil.
- [7] W.D Schindler dan P.J.Hauser, *Chemical Finishing of Textiles*, Woodhead Publishing Limited,
- [8] Leaflet Knittex FEL New, Knittex Catalyst MO Leaflet Stiffener 50Hunstman. Leaflet Ultratex STSD, Leaflet Ultratex FMI, Leaflet Fornax W, Huntsman
- [9]SNI ISO 2313:2011, Kain Tekstil – *Crease Recovery Angle*, Badan Standarisasi Nasional (BSN).